

Threshold Trust Logic*

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Abstract. Distributed processes, such as multi-party computations and collaborative product pipelines, require many entities. To formulate formal guarantees of such processes involves the gathering and evaluation of claims of the entities involved. We consider a formal logic in which modalities are used to mark the channel in which such claims are made, specifying their source and target. Formally, we see each channel as some domain of knowledge, containing both literal claims and their consequences. We can combine such channels to express whether claims were made independently by different channels, or collaboratively by pooling claims from different channels. Together, this allows us to formulate more complex combinations we call threshold channels. We can use this logic to find out which sources need to be trusted, and which targets will have received sufficient claims, in order to prove a particular guarantee. The paper is split into two parts. First, we formulate and investigate the formal properties of a modal logic expressing threshold channels. Second, we consider how to apply this to reasoning about threshold claims for distributed processes.

Keywords: Modal Logic · Distributed Systems · Formal Methods · Trust Management

1 Introduction

There is a fundamental tension between scalability and reliability. To make complex multifunctional systems, collaboration between various entities becomes a requirement. However, the more parties are involved in a process, the more difficult it becomes to verify correctness of the whole. Do the formal guarantees made by different parties properly compose and work together? Can all the parties involved be trusted to properly implement, test and verify their work?

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Many critical processes requiring formal verification are distributed across multiple entities. These include distributed security related programs, like multiparty cryptographic protocols, where multiple computers in different places perform different parts of a shared algorithm. More generally, we have collaborative processes, like those designed to produce some product (e.g. software), require different parties to work together. In such distributed processes, different parties are responsible for the correctness of different parts in the process. In order to guarantee that the whole process went smoothly, we must combine the guarantees from each of the parties involved.

The guarantee that the whole process is correct is then a statement of *trust*. We need to accept that each of the entities involved in the process is correct in their claims regarding their part of the process, and use those claims to construct a conclusion. By doing so however, we are hiding a lot of the context underpinning this conclusion. Correctness could depend on the trustworthiness of lots of parties involved, and such risk factors should be highlighted, not obfuscated. By focusing on the context in which a guarantee is made, we can better evaluate the risk and determine who is responsible for the correctness of the claim.

Just listing the parties involved in a process does not paint a complete picture. If two parties collaborate on the same part and double check each others work, for instance one writes code and the other person tests it, then we could put *more* trust in the correctness of that part. However, if two parties work on different parts of the process, we need to depend on both for correctness and should ultimately put *less* trust in the correctness of the whole. Hence, having two parties involved can, depending on the manner of collaboration, have widely different consequences on the trustworthiness of a guarantee.

In this paper we present a method handling and evaluating multiple sources in a formal logical manner, and illustrate how this can be applied to processes. We use an abstract constructive logic [16,19,25] as a foundation, with the idea that other more domain specific logics (such as those involving program correctness, cryptography, trust statements or authorization) could be embedded into it. We think this logic as a *framework* for combing statements from widely different parties, highlighting the *channels* used to communicating them. We can then use token statements as placeholders for different properties we want the process and its parts to satisfy. We use a constructive logic in particular to facilitate the building of guarantees, which is aided by the Curry-Howard correspondence expressing properties as types and proofs as programs [13]. Though constructivity is not a limitation: results should be replicable in a classical logic as well.

To add context to statements we use modalities [22,26]; unary operations in the logic. If a certain party claims a segment of the process is correct, we can use a modality signifying the channel through which this claim is made to and apply it to the claim to put it in context. This dependency on the channel will then be carried over to any statement proven using this claim. The idea is to first collect all claims made by the different parties, and both figure out whether the claims are sufficient to prove correctness of the whole process, and find the minimal sets of dependencies necessary to prove correctness of the whole. This in

turn allows us to make *threshold* claims, what is the minimum number of people we need to trust. E.g., a property could be guaranteed by using any two out of three parties' claims.

The paper is split in two distinct parts which go hand in hand. The first part is covered in Section 2, and covers the proof theory underpinning the modal logic for expressing different sources and dependencies of statements. We put particular focus on how to combine different sources into one. We revisit this first part at the end of the paper in Section 4, by considering how to deal with entities quoting and citing sources. The second part is covered in Section 3, and focuses on how model processes, like programs and codified business methodologies. We put particular emphasis on how to combine different segments of a process into one, and how to keep track of the different sources of statements while doing so. We do this in a more illustrative, hopefully intuitive manner.

Related work: Our methods for combining channels is based on *epistemic logics*, where similar concepts are used under the guise of *distributed* and *common knowledge*. Distributed knowledge, or more generally *group knowledge* has been studied in [7,24]. We mix both constructions into a single framework and prove that they act like an *distributive ordered lattice*. Unlike in epistemic logic, we do not keep the presumption that claims are actually true, as is necessary for something to be considered knowledge. Instead, we consider verified, but still not completely certain, beliefs and communications across channels, which have their roots in modal logics for *trust* [20]. Such logics have been adapted into trust management systems [18,23,1]. Strongly related to this are *authorization and access logics* [8,10,2,3] which consider automated systems in which entities sending commands and prove that they have authority to make such commands. Methods from this paper should be compatible with all such works.

2 Threshold Channels

A claim made has, besides its logical content, two contextual aspects associated to it. The first aspect is who makes the claim, which we consider the *source*. The second aspect is where the claim was made, which is considered the *target*. We think of this context as the *channel* across which the claim is made, and different combinations of aspects may have different meanings. Suppose for instance Alice is the source of some claim, she can make such a claim across different channels:

- Alice may make the claim internally, either to herself in her head or in some personal and private documentation. In this case, we think of the claim as Alice's belief, and only she has access to this information.
- Alice may make the claim publicly, by publishing it on a website or presenting it in some public venue. In this case everyone will have access to the information.
- Alice may communicate a claim privately to a colleague or client, in which case only Alice and the recipient have access to the content of the claim.

We leave the target of claims ambiguous for now, and will revisit the matter of who has access to claims till later on in the paper, in Subsection 4.1. In examples, we simply assert which claims we, as evaluator, have access to.

Let us consider first the general principles for reasoning about channels. Consider an example argument:

- If $\langle \text{an orange costs 50 cents} \rangle$
- and if $\langle \text{Charlie has 80 cents} \rangle$
- then $\langle \text{Charlie can buy an orange} \rangle$

We suppose for illustrative purposes that the above argument is irrefutably true, in the sense that everyone should accept it as such. Consider some party making claims, which we call Alice, who should be able to make the above argument. Moreover, she knows that others can also make this argument. So if Alice claims the premises of the argument are true, Alice is implying the consequence is also true. Using Alice’s claims we can derive a natural consequence which we keep in its proper context. We can make the following derivation:

- If (Alice claims) $\langle \text{an orange costs 50 cents} \rangle$
- and if (Alice claims) $\langle \text{Charlie has 80 cents} \rangle$
- then (Alice claims) $\langle \text{Charlie can buy an orange} \rangle$

This preservation of logical arguments is fundamentally what it means for the “Alice claims” channel to be logically consistent. This principle corresponds to logical axioms K and Necessity for modalities, and as such we will call it the *KN-principle*. See [4] for an investigation of such proof principles in modal logic.

Let us now consider a second possible channel: the things Bob claims. We can do the same derivation from Bob’s perspective too. If Bob claims the premises, then Bob is implying the consequence. As a result, we can consider a special channel: the things which are claimed by *both* Alice and Bob. We can apply the KN principle to this domain as well, since if both Alice and Bob claim both premises, then they both claim the consequence. This combination of channels is akin to common knowledge from epistemic logics.

Now consider a different scenario. Suppose *either* Alice or Bob claims an orange costs 50 cents, and claims Alice or Bob knows Charlie has 80 cents. From these assumptions, we cannot derive that either Alice or Bob claims the consequence. Perhaps only Alice tells the contents of Charlie’s funds, and only Bob tells the pricing of an orange, yet neither claim both facts and are responsible for the consequence. Only by pooling their claims together can we make the conclusion that Charlie can buy the orange. This combination of channels is akin to distributed knowledge from epistemic logics. We collect these two methods of combining channels in a single framework, allowing us to express more complex combinations, which we call *threshold channels*.

2.1 Logic of Channels

We assume given a set of basic channels \mathbb{A} , like beliefs, announcements and other communication channels. Let $L(\mathbb{A})$ be the free structure given by taking \mathbb{A} and closing under binary operations \times and $+$, that is:

- For each $A \in \mathbb{A}$, $[A] \in L(\mathbb{A})$.
- For each $X \in L(\mathbb{A})$ and $Y \in L(\mathbb{A})$, we have $(X + Y) \in L(\mathbb{A})$.
- For each $X \in L(\mathbb{A})$ and $Y \in L(\mathbb{A})$, we have $(X \times Y) \in L(\mathbb{A})$.

We assume given some set of basic properties \mathbb{T} we would want to reason about, which we call *tokens*. Tokens may refer to channels. Any such reference does not ad hoc have any inherent logical meaning unless separately asserted.

We inductively generate a set of formulas \mathbb{P} by taking the basic statements, and closing them under operations for conjunction (and), disjunction (or), implication (if ... then ...), and use channels as *modalities*:

- For each $a \in \mathbb{T}$, $\langle a \rangle \in \mathbb{P}$.
- For each pair $a, b \in \mathbb{P}$, $a \wedge b \in \mathbb{P}$, and $a \vee b \in \mathbb{P}$, and $a \rightarrow b \in \mathbb{P}$.
- For each pair $A \in L(\mathbb{A})$ and $b \in \mathbb{P}$, $A(b) \in L(\mathbb{A})$.

We use *sequents* to denote provable guarantees, following Gentzen's sequent calculus [12,21]. Given $a_1, \dots, a_n \in \mathbb{P}$ and $b \in \mathbb{P}$, we write:

$$a_1, \dots, a_n \vdash b$$

to express the guarantee that, given a_1 up to a_n are true, then b is true.

We assume the following basic reasoning principles:

- (Var)** $a \vdash a$ is always true.
- (Weak)** If $a_1, \dots, a_n \vdash c$ and $\{a_1, \dots, a_n\} \subseteq \{b_1, \dots, b_m\}$, then $b_1, \dots, b_m \vdash c$.
- (Cut)** If $a_1, \dots, a_n \vdash b$ and $b, c_1, \dots, c_m \vdash d$, then $a_1, \dots, a_n, c_1, \dots, c_m \vdash d$.

We deal with conjunctions, disjunctions and implication in the usual way:

- (\wedge -intro)** $a, b \vdash a \wedge b$ is true.
- (\wedge -elim)** $a \wedge b \vdash a$ and $a \wedge b \vdash b$.
- (\vee -intro)** $a \vdash a \vee b$ and $b \vdash a \vee b$.
- (\vee -elim)** If $a, c_1, \dots, c_n \vdash d$ and $b, c_1, \dots, c_n \vdash d$, then $a \vee b, c_1, \dots, c_n \vdash d$.
- (\rightarrow -intro)** If $a, c_1, \dots, c_n \vdash b$ then $c_1, \dots, c_n \vdash a \rightarrow b$.
- (\rightarrow -elim)** $a, a \rightarrow b \vdash b$.

Here “intro” stands for *introduction rule*, expressing how to prove a formula of a particular kind, and “elim” stands for *elimination rule*, expressing how a formula of a particular kind can be used to prove other statements.

The fundamental property of the modalities expressing channels is that they satisfy both Axiom K and Necessity, which can be expressed with the following derivation rule: Given some $A \in L(\mathbb{A})$, we say:

- (KN-A)** If $a_1, \dots, a_n \vdash b$, then $A(a_1), \dots, A(a_n) \vdash A(b)$.

We shall assume this principle holds for any $[A]$ where $A \in \mathbb{A}$, and then show in Lemma 1 that the rule is admissible for any $A \in L(\mathbb{A})$.

Lastly, as pertaining the \times and $+$ operations, we assert the following rules:

- (\times -intro)** $A(c) \wedge B(c) \vdash (A \times B)(c)$.

- (\times -elim) $(A \times B)(c) \vdash A(c) \wedge B(c)$.
 (+-intro) $A(c) \vdash (A + B)(c)$ and $B(c) \vdash (A + B)(c)$.
 (+-elim) If for any $a, b \vdash c$, we have $A(a), B(b), d_1, \dots, d_n \vdash e$, then $(A + B)(c), d_1, \dots, d_n \vdash e$.

We can pair up the \times rules with \wedge rules via the (Cut) rule.

In practical applications, we shall mostly forego using elimination rules for modalities directly as we are more interested in what statements and associated threshold channels we can construct. The +-elimination rule in particular is difficult to apply in general. We include elimination rules at this stage for a more fundamental reason: we can use them to prove auxiliary properties of the modalities, which can then be used to reinterpret them in a practical setting. First use of those rules being the following property:

Lemma 1. *If the KN-principle is valid for $A, B \in L(\mathbb{A})$, then it is valid for $A \times B$ and $A + B$.*

So even though we only asserted the KN-principle for basic channels, we can conclude by induction that the KN-principle holds for any $A \in L(\mathbb{A})$. Approaching the formulation in this way gives us more confidence that our method for combining channels accurately captures what it aims to describe.

Let us consider some further structure on the channels.

Definition 1. *A distributive ordered lattice is a set X equipped with a partial order \leq (reflexivity, transitivity and anti-symmetry), together with binary operations \vee and \wedge for join and meet, which distribute over each other, meaning:*

- $\forall x, y, z \in X$, $x \leq x \vee y$, $y \leq x \vee y$ and if $x \leq z$ and $y \leq z$, then $x \vee y \leq z$.
- $\forall x, y, z \in X$, $x \geq x \wedge y$, $y \geq x \wedge y$ and if $x \geq z$ and $y \geq z$, then $x \wedge y \geq z$.
- $\forall x, y, z \in X$, $x \wedge (y \vee z) = (x \wedge y) \vee (x \wedge z)$, and $x \vee (y \wedge z) = (x \vee y) \wedge (x \vee z)$.

For two modalities $A, B \in L(\mathbb{A})$, we write $A \sqsubseteq B$ if for any $c \in \mathbb{P}$, $A(c) \vdash B(c)$. We write $A \equiv B$ if $A \sqsubseteq B$ and $B \sqsubseteq A$. Let $L'(\mathbb{A})$ be the set $L(\mathbb{A})$ quotiented over \equiv , meaning its elements are equivalence classes of modalities.

Lemma 2. *The set of modalities $L'(\mathbb{A})$ forms a distributive ordered lattice, with \sqsubseteq as partial order, $+$ as join operation and \times as meet operation.*

Proof. Note that \sqsubseteq is a partial order: reflexivity via the (Var) rule, transitivity via the (Cut) rule, and anti-symmetry since we quotient over \equiv . There is a full proof of the rest of the properties in the appendix. We show for illustration the following join property of $+$: $A \sqsubseteq C$ and $B \sqsubseteq C$, then $(A + B) \sqsubseteq C$.

Let $c \in \mathbb{P}$ and take $b, c \in \mathbb{P}$ such that $a, b \vdash c$. Then $A(a) \vdash C(a)$, and $B(b) \vdash C(b)$, and $C(a), C(b) \vdash C(c)$. Combining those with the (Cut) rule, we get $A(a), B(b) \vdash C(c)$. This holds for all such a, b , so $(A + B)(c) \vdash C(c)$.

As a consequence of the above, we have some further properties, such as the fact that $+$ and \times form idempotent, commutative and associative operations.

See e.g. [6] for further details on order lattices. Furthermore, with distributivity we can show that every channel A is equivalent to a channel of the form:

$$((A_1^1 + \cdots + A_{n_1}^1) \times \cdots \times (A_1^m + \cdots + A_{n_m}^m))$$

where each $A_i^j \in \mathbb{A}$.

For example, $((A \times B) + (A \times C) + (B \times C)) \equiv ((A+B) \times (A+C) \times (B+C))$. This particular channel is trustworthy if at least two out of the three channels A , B and C are trustworthy. So any one channel being unreliable does not necessarily invalidate the entire channel. We call this particular combination of channels a *2 out of 3 threshold* channel, and denote:

$$\text{2of3}(A, B, C) := ((A + B) \times (A + C) \times (B + C))$$

The above proofs were made solely based on the proof rules we used. In particular, it show-cases how the (+-elim) rule helps establish basic principles. In practice though, we shall mostly forego the use of the (+-elim) rule, opting instead to use the lattice structure directly. By reverse engineering, we can formulate the following proof rule:

(Lat) If $A \sqsubseteq B$ according to the lattice structure, then $A(c) \vdash B(c)$.

2.2 Regarding Kripke Models

Kripke models for intuitionistic modal logics have been explored extensively in the literature, for instance in [22,26]. Most of the proof rules we considered are in line with the usual intuitionistic logics, except for the (+-elim) rule. Though we mostly use this rule as motivation to assert statements like $(A+B) \equiv (B+A)$ implied by the (Lat) rule, it is possible to find reasonable Kripke models for which the rule is sound. Such models have to bridge the gap between the nebulous concept of *possible worlds* and what can be concretely expressed with formulas.

A Kripke frame exists of a set of worlds W , a preorder \leq on W , for each token $t \in \mathbb{T}$ a subset $S_t \subseteq W$ which is upwards closed w.r.t. \leq , and for each basic channel $A \in \mathbb{A}$ a relation \bar{A} on W . These relations are extended to relations for each $A \in L(\mathbb{A})$, by taking $\bar{A} \times \bar{B} = \bar{A} \cup \bar{B}$ and $\bar{A} + \bar{B} = \bar{A} \cap \bar{B}$. We then inductively define a satisfiability relation for formulas $\models \subseteq W \times \mathbb{P}$ as follows:

- $w \models \langle t \rangle$ iff $w \in S_t$.
- $w \models a \wedge b$ iff $w \models a$ and $w \models b$.
- $w \models a \vee b$ iff $w \models a$ or $w \models b$.
- $w \models a \rightarrow b$ iff for any $w' \in W$, if $w \leq w'$ and $w' \models a$ then $w' \models b$.
- $w \models A(b)$ iff for any $w', v' \in W$, if $w \leq w' \bar{A} v'$ then $v' \models b$.

The above Kripke frames validate all proof rules except (+-elim) (see e.g. [22]). We consider two further properties:

- (I)** For each $A \in \mathbb{A}$, if $w \bar{A} v \leq v'$ then $w \bar{A} v'$.
- (II)** $\forall w \in W$ and $A \in \mathbb{A}$, there is a formula $|w, A|$ such that $v \models |w, A|$ iff $w \bar{A} v$.

Both properties are extendable to any $A \in L(\mathbb{A})$. The first property is not very restrictive since the satisfiability is monotone: for each Kripke frame not satisfying 1 there is an equivalent one (in terms of it having the same satisfiability relation) satisfying 1. The second property is more imposing, and asserts that everyone's viewpoint can be defined by some concrete logical statement. This is in line with the idea that worlds express concrete provable and observable facts, and Kripke frames do not hold information beyond this expressibility. One approach to satisfying this property is to have a finite number of worlds W , and sufficient tokens $t_w \in \mathbb{T}$ expressing the observations related to existing in a world $w \in W$, that is: $v \models t_w$ if and only if $v \leq w$.

Lemma 3. *Kripke frames satisfying (I) and (II) validate the (+-elim) rule.*

3 Modelling Processes

We investigate how the logic of threshold channels can be used to model threshold guarantees of processes. By process we mean a series of steps or subprocesses, moving from one state to another, which together compose into a complete process we want to prove correctness of. Different agents may be experts of, or be responsible for, different parts of the process. As such, to prove correctness of the whole, we need to combine statements from different sources.

We keep ambiguous what kind of processes we are describing. The fundamental idea is that a process is a series of actions and transitions, which takes some starting state and transforms it into some final state. Correctness of such a process can be summarized as a series of pre-condition post-condition statements, expressing that, if the starting state satisfies some *precondition*, then once the process is finished, the final state will satisfy some *postcondition*.

Examples of such processes include:

- *Product Pipelines*, in which several companies or departments within a company collaboratively create a product, each working on different parts. Correctness of the resulting product depends on claims of correctness of the different parts, and checking whether the statements can be combined.
- *Code Evaluation*, which take the internal state of a machine and executes a series of algorithmic steps to produce some final state. Different software engineers may have written different pieces of the code, and different testers may have tested different parts. To prove program correctness, claims from multiple agents would need to be combined.

3.1 Process Correctness Done Abstractly

The main method for proving that a process is correct is to prove its specification. That is, given the proposed starting conditions, if we go through the process, we get to a state satisfying some final conditions. These conditions can be declared in several ways, either using a stateful transition system with conditions on input and output state, or more prominently for programs using a *Hoare logic* [17]. In

this work, we focus more on the distributed essence of the verification, and leave further instantiations of properties and specifications to be considered in future work, dependent on applications.

We shall for conciseness highlight two main token statements:

- $\langle \text{start} \rangle$, stating that the input and starting state before the process is run satisfies some prespecified starting conditions.
- $\langle \text{end} \rangle$, stating that the output and ending state after the process is run satisfies some prespecified ending conditions.

So we shall assume that the process starts in some starting state, and consider the final state resulting from running the process. We can then write $\langle \text{start} \rangle \rightarrow \langle \text{end} \rangle$ to mean that, if the initial state and input meet the criteria specified in $\langle \text{start} \rangle$, then the final state and output meet the criteria specified in $\langle \text{end} \rangle$.¹

We can split up the proof of correctness into segments, declaring intermediate points in the process. So we may use other formula $\langle a \rangle$, $\langle b \rangle$, $\langle c \rangle$, ... to say that at particular points in the execution of the process, the state at that point satisfies some prespecified condition.

Suppose for instance that we have two intermediate states $\langle a \rangle$ and $\langle b \rangle$, then we can prove correctness by combining statements $\langle \text{start} \rangle \rightarrow \langle a \rangle$, $\langle a \rangle \rightarrow \langle b \rangle$, and $\langle b \rangle \rightarrow \langle \text{end} \rangle$. We can illustrate those statements with a graph:

Given these assumptions, we can further derive other implications:

Such derivations can be made in constructive logic (see Section 2) as follows: By (\rightarrow -elim), $\langle \text{start} \rangle, \langle \text{start} \rangle \rightarrow \langle a \rangle \vdash \langle a \rangle$, and $\langle a \rangle, \langle a \rangle \rightarrow \langle b \rangle \vdash \langle b \rangle$, and $\langle b \rangle, \langle b \rangle \rightarrow \langle \text{end} \rangle \vdash \langle \text{end} \rangle$, hence we get $\langle \text{start} \rangle, \langle \text{start} \rangle \rightarrow \langle a \rangle, \langle a \rangle \rightarrow \langle b \rangle, \langle b \rangle \rightarrow \langle \text{end} \rangle \vdash \langle \text{end} \rangle$, so $\langle \text{start} \rangle \rightarrow \langle a \rangle, \langle a \rangle \rightarrow \langle b \rangle, \langle b \rangle \rightarrow \langle \text{end} \rangle \vdash \langle \text{start} \rangle \rightarrow \langle \text{end} \rangle$

3.2 Correctness via Channels

Each channel $A \in L(\mathbb{A})$ allows us to specify the source and target of a claim. Let us for instance consider three sources making claims: Alice, Bob and Charlie, with *us* as recipient. We can illustrate a set of claims as follows:

¹ Alternatively, we could use modalities to mark moments in time, but this may make the situations more complicated than needed. We assert for simplicity that each $\langle \dots \rangle$ statement considers a property in a particular moment or period in time.

Here we use a rounded box to mark different channels. The above expresses the statements:

- [Alice]($\langle \text{start} \rangle \rightarrow \langle a \rangle$)
- [Bob]($\langle a \rangle \rightarrow \langle b \rangle$)
- [Charlie]($\langle b \rangle \rightarrow \langle \text{end} \rangle$)

Given our choice of basic token statements, we can interpret these statements as follows. Alice is claiming the start of the process, up to a , is correct. Similarly, Bob claims the middle of process, going from a to b , is correct. Lastly, Charlie claims the end of the program is correct. We use color-coding for the channels, with three primary colours associated to our three sources.

Combining all sources into a single source, we have an argument for the correctness of the whole program, requiring trust in all parties involved:

This expresses that $([Alice] + ([Bob] + [Charlie]))(\langle \text{start} \rangle \rightarrow \langle \text{end} \rangle)$, and this is provable from the assumptions using our logic. We coloured this black, to symbolize the mixing of the three channels.

3.3 Rules for Combining Channels

Before looking at further examples, let us consider some general rules of the logic graphically, following the introduction rules for channels.

We can combine sources by collecting all statements claimed in either source, and making derivations. We make the following derivation, mixing colours:

Alternatively, we can consider independent claims, overlapping the boxes:

Lastly, we can always rewrite a channel into another channel if they are logically equivalent, as established in Lemma 2.

Risk mitigation: We consider two examples. In this initial scenario, we have Alice and Bob each verifying half of the process, and Charlie verifying the process as a whole, for instance as an auditor, manager or program tester.

Applying the rules from before, we can first combine Alice and Bobs claims to create a claim of correctness for the whole process:

We can mitigate the risk of Alice and Bob’s combined proof by considering Charlie’s independent verification:

Alternatively, suppose Alice, Bob and Charlie each claim correctness of two parts of the process in the following configuration:

We then have that each pair of two channels can be combined to give a claim of correctness of the whole process. We end up with the statement that any two out of three channels claim correctness of the whole:

3.4 Branching and Converging in Processes

Since we use a full logic as a basis, we can express more complex process steps. We base the diagrammatic notation of such steps on [15], using *string diagrams* to express more complex relations between states of processes. Firstly, we consider *case distinctions*, modelling the possibility for multiple possible outputs, considering multiple cases or nondeterministic behaviour. Logically, we can write $\langle a \rangle \rightarrow \langle b \rangle \vee \langle c \rangle$ to say that from $\langle a \rangle$, we either get $\langle b \rangle$ or $\langle c \rangle$. In such scenarios, one must deal with each of the two outcomes. We can illustrate case distinctions as forked arrows:

In this example, see that we can get either intermediate property $\langle a \rangle$ or $\langle b \rangle$. If we can get to the end from each of the two possibilities, we get a proof of correctness: From $\langle \text{start} \rangle \rightarrow \langle a \rangle \vee \langle b \rangle$, and $\langle a \rangle \rightarrow \langle \text{end} \rangle$ and $\langle b \rangle \rightarrow \langle \text{end} \rangle$, we can derive $\langle \text{start} \rangle \rightarrow \langle \text{end} \rangle$.

Dual to case distinctions, we may also require multiple assumptions in order to get a derivation. We can use the formula $\langle a \rangle \wedge \langle b \rangle \rightarrow \langle c \rangle$ to say that we need both $\langle a \rangle$ and $\langle b \rangle$ to derive $\langle c \rangle$. In such scenarios, one must show both conditions are met. We can illustrate case distinctions as merging arrows:

In this example, see that we need both intermediate property $\langle a \rangle$ and $\langle b \rangle$ in order to derive correctness of the output. If we can derive each intermediate property from the start, we get a proof of correctness: From $\langle \text{start} \rangle \rightarrow \langle a \rangle$, and $\langle \text{start} \rangle \rightarrow \langle b \rangle$, and $\langle a \rangle \wedge \langle b \rangle \rightarrow \langle \text{end} \rangle$, we derive $\langle \text{start} \rangle \rightarrow \langle \text{end} \rangle$.

Take the following final example. Alice and Bob collaborate on some process, with Alice doing the core work and Bob helping out if necessary. Alice may either get to $\langle a \rangle$ or $\langle b \rangle$, and in case of $\langle a \rangle$ she can finish the process herself. Bob on the other hand initiates his part of the process by getting to $\langle c \rangle$. Then in case Alice can't finish the process on her own (the case of $\langle b \rangle$), Bob can jump in by contributing his own guarantee $\langle c \rangle$ and finishing the process.

In this case, Alice’s problematic intermediate case given by $\langle b \rangle$, and Bob’s need for a $\langle b \rangle$ to finish the process complement each other perfectly, and we can derive that in the combined Alice + Bob source, $\langle \text{start} \rangle \rightarrow \langle \text{end} \rangle$ holds. If moreover Charlie comes in and claims both $\langle \text{start} \rangle \rightarrow \langle a \rangle$ and $\langle c \rangle \rightarrow \langle \text{end} \rangle$, we can also conclude $2\text{of}3(\text{Alice}, \text{Bob}, \text{Charlie})(\langle \text{start} \rangle \rightarrow \langle \text{end} \rangle)$.

3.5 Note on Estimating Risks

To evaluate the strength of a derived statement, we must consider the probability that a certain channel is correct and trustworthy. This is difficult to evaluate in general, however we can make comparisons. Take for instance Alice + Bob, which is a less reliable source than Alice, since we need to rely on two sources instead of one. On the other hand, the source Alice \times Bob is more reliable than Alice, since we have Bob around for a second opinion.

Given some function $\rho : \mathbb{A} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ expressing the *risk* or probability that a certain basic channel is unreliable, we can extend this to a risk function $\rho^* : L(\mathbb{A}) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ on threshold channels. This extension is straightforward, using the fact that: $A \times B$ is unreliable if both A and B are unreliable, and $A + B$ is unreliable if either A or B is unreliable.

This leaves the matter of choosing ρ . It is difficult to determine whether one source is more reliable than the other, even more so to associate a specific risk value. We can simplify the estimation by asserting that each source has a comparable risk, taking the risk factor to be some constant ε . To get a quick estimation, we can take $\varepsilon = 0.1$. The following table gives some examples:

Source	ε -risk	$\varepsilon = 0.1$
Alice	ε	0.1
Alice + Bob	$2\varepsilon - \varepsilon^2$	0.19
Alice + Bob + Charlie	$3\varepsilon - 3\varepsilon^2 + \varepsilon^3$	0.271
Alice \times Bob	ε^2	0.01
Alice \times Bob \times Charlie	ε^3	0.001
(Alice + Bob) \times Charlie	$2\varepsilon^2 - \varepsilon^3$	0.019
$2\text{of}3(\text{Alice}, \text{Bob}, \text{Charlie})$	$3\varepsilon^2 - 2\varepsilon^3$	0.028

4 Nested Claims

Up to this point, we have mostly considered claims being gathered into a single framework. We saw ourselves as some entity having access to all available claims. In practice, this may not always be the case. If claims of correctness are not publicly shared, but instead only privately send to certain individuals, situations arise where such claims may be further distributed by others. In such cases, you may come across a claim, not as directly given by the source, but forwarded by one or more middlemen. We consider this situation in our logic.

Given two channels $A, B \in L(\mathbb{A})$, we can *nest* them. That is, given a statement $c \in \mathbb{P}$, we can write $A(B(c))$ to write that channel A claims that c has been

communicated through channel B . For instance $\text{Alice}(\text{Bob}(c))$ means that Alice claims that Bob claims c holds. This is a way of *quoting* someone else's claim, which may be necessary if Bob hasn't made the claim public.

From the perspective of trust, nesting channels gets a bit nuanced. To accept c as true when faced with the claim $A(B(c))$ requires us to trust both A and B . We must trust A to not misquote the claim from domain B , and we must trust B to not lie about the original claim. From this perspective, we could interpret it as $(A + B)(c)$. However, it is easier to trust someone to correctly quote a source than it is to trust someone regarding a fundamental claim. Moreover, A quoting B could also be seen as an endorsement of the claim, so it could also be interpreted as $(A \times B)(c)$ instead.

In short, the role of the channels in a nested statement is not created equal. As such, we avoid simplifying such statements. Instead, we look at properties of nestings in general.

Lemma 4. *The following properties hold:*

1. $A(C(e)), B(D(e)) \vdash (A \times B)((C + D)(e))$,
2. $A(C(e)), B(D(e)) \vdash (A + B)((C \times D)(e))$,
3. *If $e, f \vdash g$, then $A(C(e)), B(D(f)) \vdash (A + B)((C + D)(g))$.*

Proof. We prove the three properties separately:

1. Since $C(e) \vdash (C + D)(e)$ we have $A(C(e)) \vdash A((C + D)(e))$. Similarly $B(D(e)) \vdash B((C + D)(e))$. Combined with $A((C + D)(e)), B((C + D)(e)) \vdash (A \times B)((C + D)(e))$, we get $A(C(e)), B(D(e)) \vdash (A \times B)((C + D)(e))$.
2. Note that $A(C(e)) \vdash (A + B)(C(e))$ and $B(D(e)) \vdash (A + B)(D(e))$. Since $C(e), D(e) \vdash (C \times D)(e)$, we get $(A + B)(C(e)), (A + B)(D(e)) \vdash (A + B)((C \times D)(e))$ by the KN-principle. Hence $A(C(e)), B(D(e)) \vdash (A + B)((C \times D)(e))$.
3. If $e, f \vdash g$, then $C(e), D(f) \vdash (C + D)(g)$, and $(A + B)(C(e)), (A + B)(D(f)) \vdash (A + B)((C + D)(g))$. Since $A(C(e)) \vdash (A + B)(C(e))$, and $B(D(f)) \vdash (A + B)(D(f))$, we conclude $A(C(e)), B(D(f)) \vdash (A + B)((C + D)(g))$.

Illustration of property 3 from above. We draw nested claims as nested boxes, separating them from parallel claims, which are drawn with intersecting boxes.

Example 1. Suppose we have:

- $(X \times Y)(A(\langle \text{start} \rangle \rightarrow \langle a \rangle \wedge \langle b \rangle \rightarrow \langle \text{end} \rangle))$,
- $(X \times Z)(B(\langle \text{start} \rangle \rightarrow \langle a \rangle \wedge \langle a \rangle \rightarrow \langle b \rangle))$, and
- $(Y \times Z)(C(\langle a \rangle \rightarrow \langle b \rangle \wedge \langle b \rangle \rightarrow \langle \text{end} \rangle))$,

then

$$- \text{2of3}(X, Y, Z)(\text{2of3}(A, B, C)(\langle \text{start} \rangle \rightarrow \langle \text{end} \rangle)),$$

We can think of this as the following scenario. Alice, Bob and Charlie are making claims of correctness of parts of the process. X , Y and Z evaluate and forwards these claims to us, but none of X , Y and Z have access to all of Alice, Bobs and Charlie's claims.

The consequence is we need to trust two out of three of X , Y and Z in order to believe that all claims made by Alice, Bob and Charlie are actually legitimate. We then need to trust two out of three of Alice, Bob, and Charlie to properly compose all segments into one guarantee of correctness of the whole.

4.1 Awareness Axioms

Since each channel has a target, and this target in practice determines who can see what claims are communicated over the channel, we should be able to make some further derivations based on that. We consider the principle of *awareness* and *quoting*. Suppose given channels A and B where the source of A has access to the target of B . Then we can consider the following property:

$$A \triangleleft B \text{ is the assertion that for any } c, B(c) \vdash A(B(c)).$$

We say in this case that channel A is aware of channel B . The precise meaning of this awareness depends on the nature of the channel. If A expresses the knowledge or belief of some source, then awareness can be interpreted literally: if channel B makes a claim, the source of A knows and believes that the claim has been made. If A instead involves further communication to some other target, the axiom instead expresses the act of forwarding to that target everything communicated over channel B . This latter interpretation is useful in product pipelines, where a middlemen collects claims made by subcontractors and forwards those claims to a client or collaborator down the line.

In general, awareness of A in B depends on whether the source of A has access to the target of B , and whether the source of A is willing to forward everything from B through A . Obviously, the statement $A \triangleleft B$ holds up to equivalence of channels. Using logical derivation rules, we can prove the following properties:

Lemma 5. *The following properties hold:*

1. If $A \triangleleft B$ and $A \triangleleft C$, then $A \triangleleft (B \times C)$ and $A \triangleleft (B + C)$.
2. If $A \triangleleft C$, then $(A + B) \triangleleft C$.
3. If $A \triangleleft C$ and $B \triangleleft C$, then $(A \times B) \triangleleft C$.

Example 2. Suppose we have $X \triangleleft A$, $X \triangleleft B$, $Y \triangleleft A$, $Y \triangleleft C$, $Z \triangleleft B$ and $Z \triangleleft C$, then we can derive using the above lemma that $\text{2of3}(X, Y, Z) \triangleleft \text{2of3}(A, B, C)$. So if we were to revisit the last example of Subsection 3.3, and consider:

$$- A(\langle \text{start} \rangle \rightarrow \langle \text{a} \rangle \wedge \langle \text{b} \rangle \rightarrow \langle \text{end} \rangle),$$

- $B(\langle \text{start} \rangle \rightarrow \langle a \rangle \wedge \langle a \rangle \rightarrow \langle b \rangle)$, and
- $C(\langle a \rangle \rightarrow \langle b \rangle \wedge \langle b \rangle \rightarrow \langle \text{end} \rangle)$,

then similarly to Example 1 we can derive:

- $2\text{of}3(X, Y, Z)(2\text{of}3(A, B, C)(\langle \text{start} \rangle \rightarrow \langle \text{end} \rangle))$,

5 Conclusions

In this paper, we focused primarily on how to combine and evaluate statements from different channels. We used a modal logic, with modalities expressing certain combinations of channels. These modalities satisfied the modal axioms of K and Necessity, as well as axioms related to their interplay, as pertaining their lattice like structure. Much of the literature considering modal logic for trust and authorization (outlined at the end of the introduction) consider other kinds of axioms related to the behaviour of nesting modalities as well.

We briefly considered such axioms in the Subsection 4.1, which relates to trust and authorization logics. For instance, suppose Bob tells Alice($\langle c \rangle$), then you could further conclude that Alice believes(Bob tells Alice($\langle c \rangle$)), since Alice will be aware of what she has been told. The logic presented in this paper is rather agnostic regarding this interplay between channels, but nothing stops us from adding even more axioms. For instance, it may be convenient to mark *public knowledge* with a special modality, allowing public statements to be adopted by all channels.

We use channels as fundamental building in our logic because they are methods for communicating claims from one domain to another. As such, they are more abstract and general than modalities expressing *belief*, *knowledge*, *messages*, and *announcements*. Using modalities to shift between different domains is also in line with the interpretation of modalities in dependent modal logic [5,9]. There they start by defining a collection of objects, akin to our sources and targets, and define morphisms between them, akin to our channels. As such, modal dependent logic would be a suitable place to prove and build guarantees of the kind formulated in this paper.

To aid automatization of proof derivation, we can consider a decidable fragment of our logic. Here we forego the (+-elim) rule and instead use the (Lat) rule, which was shown to be admissible in the logic in Lemma 2. This fragment is *decidable*, that is; there is an algorithm which given some formulas $a_1, \dots, a_n, b \in \mathbb{P}$, decides whether the sequent $a_1, \dots, a_n \vdash b$ is provable. This decidability can be shown by fitting it into existing decidable modal logic frameworks used in for instance [11,14].

We can do this by taking as modalities non-empty finite subsets of \mathbb{A} representing + combinations of basic channels. We equip this with the partial order expressing subsets. Constructive modal logics with modalities satisfying axiom K and N, as well as an axiom of implication between modalities via some partial order, fits within the framework of [11], and hence are decidable. More general channels from \mathbb{A} can be expressed in this logic as syntactic sugar. Note that each

element of $L(\mathbb{A})$ is, according to the (Lat) rule equivalent to a \times combination of $+$ combinations of basic channels. As such, we can express each channel as a conjunctive (\wedge) combination of modalities.

It would be curious to figure out whether the ($+$ -elim) rule is actually admissible in the decidable fragment of the logic. In part, this would depend on there being enough tokens, similar to considerations made in our discussion of Kripke models in Subsection 2.2. This is an interesting question for future research.

Appendix: Additional Proofs

In this appendix, we lay out proofs for the Lemmas in the main text.

Proof (Lemma 1). Suppose that, if $a_1, \dots, a_n \vdash b$ then $A(a_1), \dots, A(a_n) \vdash A(b)$ and $B(a_1), \dots, B(a_n) \vdash A(b)$.

Note that $(A \times B)(a_i) \vdash A(a_i) \wedge B(b_i)$, and $A(a_i) \wedge B(b_i) \vdash A(a_i)$, so $(A \times B)(a_1), \dots, (A \times B)(a_n) \vdash A(b)$. Similarly $(A \times B)(a_1), \dots, (A \times B)(a_n) \vdash B(b)$. Since $A(b), B(b) \vdash A(b) \wedge B(b)$ and $A(b) \wedge B(b) \vdash (A \times B)(b)$, we can conclude that $(A \times B)(a_1), \dots, (A \times B)(a_n) \vdash (A \times B)(b)$.

Take x_i and y_i such that $x_i, y_i \vdash a_i$, for each i . Note that $x_1, \dots, x_n \vdash x_1 \wedge \dots \wedge x_n$ and $y_1, \dots, y_n \vdash y_1 \wedge \dots \wedge y_n$, so $A(x_1), \dots, A(x_n) \vdash A(x_1 \wedge \dots \wedge x_n)$ and $B(y_1), \dots, B(y_n) \vdash B(y_1 \wedge \dots \wedge y_n)$, hence $A(x_1), \dots, A(x_n) \vdash (A + B)(x_1 \wedge \dots \wedge x_n)$ and $B(y_1), \dots, B(y_n) \vdash (A + B)(y_1 \wedge \dots \wedge y_n)$. Note that $x_1 \wedge \dots \wedge x_n, y_1 \wedge \dots \wedge y_n \vdash a_1 \wedge \dots \wedge a_n$ by reasoning about conjunctions, and that $a_1 \wedge \dots \wedge a_n \vdash b$. So $(A + B)(x_1 \wedge \dots \wedge x_n), (A + B)(y_1 \wedge \dots \wedge y_n) \vdash (A + B)(b)$. Combining all with (Cut), we get: $A(x_1), \dots, A(x_n), B(y_1), \dots, B(y_n) \vdash (A + B)(b)$.

Considering this is for all $x_i, y_i \vdash a_i$, then by applying the ($+$ -elim) rule iteratively we derive $(A + B)(a_1), \dots, (A + B)(a_n) \vdash (A + B)(b)$.

Proof (Lemma 2, rest of proof). We have argued that \sqsubseteq is a partial order.

For the additional join property of $+$, note that by ($+$ -intro) rule, $A(c) \vdash (A + B)(c)$ and $B(c) \vdash (A + B)(c)$, hence $A \sqsubseteq (A + B)$ and $B \sqsubseteq (A + B)$.

For the meet properties of \times , note that by the (\times -elim) rules, $(A \times B)(c) \vdash A(c)$ and $(A \times B)(c) \vdash B(c)$, so $A \times B \sqsubseteq A$ and $A \times B \sqsubseteq B$. If $C \sqsubseteq A$ and $C \sqsubseteq B$, then for any $c \in \mathbb{P}$, $C(c) \vdash A(c)$ and $C(c) \vdash B(c)$. By the (\times -intro) rule, $A(c), B(c) \vdash (A \times B)(c)$, so using the (Cut) rule, $C(c) \vdash (A \times B)(c)$, hence $C \sqsubseteq (A \times B)$.

Now for distributivity. Take some c and take a, b such that $a, b \vdash c$. Then $A(c), B(a) \vdash (A \times B)(a \vee c)$ and $A(c), C(b) \vdash (A \times C)(b \vee c)$ and $(A \times B)(a \vee c), (A \times C)(b \vee c) \vdash ((A \times B) + (A \times C))(c)$ since $a \vee c, b \vee c \vdash c$, hence $A(c), B(a), C(b) \vdash ((A \times B) + (A \times C))(c)$. Since this is for any a, b such that $a, b \vdash c$, we conclude $A(c), (B + C)(c) \vdash ((A \times B) + (A \times C))(c)$ and hence $(A \times (B + C))(c) \vdash ((A \times B) + (A \times C))(c)$. We conclude that $(A \times (B + C)) \sqsubseteq ((A \times B) + (A \times C))$.

Take some c and let a, b such that $a, b \vdash c$. Then $A(a), B(b) \vdash (A + B)(c)$, and $A(a), C(b) \vdash (A + C)(c)$, so $A(a), B(b), C(b) \vdash ((A + B) \times (A + C))(c)$. Since $(B \times C)(b) \vdash B(b) \wedge C(b)$, we furthermore get that $A(a), (B \times C)(b) \vdash ((A + B) \times (A + C))(c)$. Since this is for any a, b such that $a, b \vdash c$, we can derive

$(A + (B \times C))(c) \vdash ((A + B) \times (A + C))(c)$. We conclude that $(A + (B \times C)) \sqsubseteq ((A + B) \times (A + C))$.

For the converse, note that $((A + B) \times (A + C))(c) \vdash (((A + B) \times A) + ((A + B) \times C))(c)$, which proves $((A \times A) + (B \times A) + ((A \times C) + (B \times C)))(c)$, which proves $(A + (B \times A) + (A \times C) + (B \times C))(c)$, which proves $(A + (B \times C))(c)$. The other converse goes similarly.

Proof (Lemma 3). Suppose given some Kripke frame satisfying properties 1 and 2. We write $\models a$ if $w \models a$ for all $w \in W$. Note that $a_1, \dots, a_n \vdash b$ holds if and only if $\vdash (a_1 \wedge \dots \wedge a_n) \rightarrow b$. So w models the sequent if $w \models (a_1 \wedge \dots \wedge a_n) \rightarrow b$.

Suppose for any a, b such that $\models (a \wedge b) \rightarrow c$, we have $\models (A(a) \wedge B(b)) \rightarrow d$, the assumption of the (+-elim) rule.

Take $w, w' \in W$ such that $w \leq w' \models (A + B)(c)$, so $\forall v' \in W$, if $w' \bar{A}v'$ and $w' \bar{B}v'$ it holds that $v' \models c$. Note that:

- $w' \models A(|w', A|)$ by definition of $|w', A|$.
- $w' \models B(|w', A| \rightarrow c)$, since given $v', v \in W$ such that $w' \bar{B}v' \leq v \models |w', A|$, we have $w' \bar{B}v$ by property 1, and $w' \bar{A}v$ by definition of $|w', A|$. So by assumption, $v \models c$.

Since $\models (|w', A| \wedge (|w', A| \rightarrow c)) \rightarrow c$, we know that $\models (A(|w', A|) \wedge B(|w', A| \rightarrow c)) \rightarrow d$. Hence, since $w \leq w' \models (A(|w', A|) \wedge B(|w', A| \rightarrow c))$ we have $w' \models d$.

This is for any w' for which $w \leq w'$, we conclude that $w \models (A + B)(c) \rightarrow d$. This is for every w , so $\models (A + B)(c) \rightarrow d$.

Proof (Lemma 5).

1. Suppose $A \triangleleft B$ and $A \triangleleft C$.

Take some $d \in \mathbb{P}$, then $B(d) \vdash A(B(d))$ and $C(d) \vdash A(C(d))$, and since $B(d), C(d) \vdash (B \times C)(d)$ we have $A(B(d)), A(C(d)) \vdash A((B \times C)(d))$. We conclude $(B \times C)(d) \vdash A((B \times C)(d))$.

Let b, c such that $b, c \vdash d$. Now, $B(b) \vdash A(B(b))$ and $C(c) \vdash A(C(c))$, and since $B(b), C(c) \vdash (B + C)(d)$ we get $A(B(b)), A(C(c)) \vdash A((B + C)(d))$. So $B(b), C(c) \vdash A((B + C)(d))$, and since this is for any b, c such that $b, c \vdash d$, we can conclude that $(B + C)(d) \vdash A((B + C)(d))$.

2. This property are relatively straightforward, since $A(C(d)) \vdash (A + B)(C(d))$,
3. Straightforward, since $A(C(d)), B(C(d)) \vdash (A \times B)(C(d))$.

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